

FATIGUE PERFORMANCE AND DAMAGE
ACCUMULATION IN UNIDIRECTIONAL
GLASS REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This work examines damage initiation and accumulation in glass reinforced composite systems. Several unidirectional glass reinforced thermoplastic and thermoset composites are monitored during three point bend static and fatigue loading. The spatial and time distribution of accumulated damage is monitored using acoustic emission techniques. Damaged samples are also statically tested to determine residual mechanical properties, and examined microscopically to define the damage state. Damage mechanics models are developed to demonstrate how the damage accumulation and distribution leads to changes in mechanical properties such as stiffness and residual strength.

INTRODUCTION

Glass reinforced composites are being used in more and more structural and semi-structural applications. Examples range from automotive applications such as bumper beams, door frames, drive shafts, and load floors to industrial applications such as gears, machine housings, construction materials, and crane booms.

As a number of structural and semi-structural applications continues to grow, it becomes important to characterize the long term durability and damage tolerance of these materials and understand the process of damage accumulation and propagation. This understanding will ultimately allow us to design and produce longer lasting and more damage tolerant composite structures.

In this work, the initiation and accumulation of fatigue damage is examined both experimentally and through damage mechanics model development. In both cases, changes in the spatial and time distribution of accumulated damage is related to changes in bulk properties such as residual strength and bending stiffness [1,2,3].

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

This paper examines damage initiation and accumulation during three point bend fatigue for several unidirectional glass reinforced thermoplastic and thermoset composites. The thermoplastic matrix resins studied are nylon and polyethylene terephthalate (PET). The thermoset matrix resins are standard grades of epoxy and unsaturated polyester. Glass loadings in all composites ranged from 50 to 60 percent by volume.

The three point bend test geometry follows ASTM D790 with a span to depth ratio of 16. All materials are tested at room temperature and humidity. Samples are fatigued by cycling the load sinusoidally from a selected level to one tenth of that level ($R=0.1$) on a Material Test System (MTS) 880 hydraulic test frame. Minimum and maximum values of both load and deflection are recorded and used to calculate the apparent bending stiffness at each fatigue cycle. This stiffness is defined as the cyclic load range divided by the cyclic deflection range for a given cycle, and is equivalent to the dynamic spring constant of the coupon beam. Many researchers have related changes in apparent bending stiffness to damage accumulation in composite materials [4,5,6]. Figure 1 shows apparent bending stiffness versus flexural fatigue cycles for a typical coupon measured in our laboratory.

Damage accumulation is monitored during both fatigue and static loading using acoustic emission (AE) techniques. A variety of studies in the literature have demonstrated using similar AE techniques to monitor damage accumulation in composite materials [2,7,8,9]. The AE response of each sample is recorded through two piezoelectric transducers, one mounted at each end of the sample coupon. This response is amplified, filtered, and recorded using a "LOCAN-AT" system supplied by Physical Acoustics Corporation (PAC). Using two transducers allows monitoring both the spatial and time distribution of the acoustic signal. Acoustic parameters recorded include signal amplitude, duration, location, and rise time, along with total accumulated hits and acoustic energy. A more detailed schematic of the AE test arrangement is shown in Figure 2.

Damaged (fatigued) samples are also statically tested to determine residual mechanical properties, and examined microscopically to further define the damage state. The internal damage state (as indicated by AE signatures and photomicrographs) can then be related to measured changes in mechanical properties such as residual strength and bending stiffness [2,5,6].

Figure 1 Measured apparent bending stiffness versus fatigue cycles for a three point bend flexural fatigue experiment.

Figure 2 Schematic diagram of acoustic emission test arrangement.

MODEL DEVELOPMENT

A simple damage mechanics model is also developed to predict the accumulation of damage during three point bend fatigue. This model is used to calculate the damage state and stress distribution at each fatigue cycle at any point in a flex bar. It is also used to predict how bulk properties (such as apparent bending stiffness) change during a fatigue test for different damage states

This two-dimensional finite element model is based on modifying classical linear beam theory to account for the effect of local damage at each point in the test bar [1,3]. Damage accumulation is modeled through a constitutive equation based on Kachanov's Law, which describes the local rate of damage accumulation in terms of the local stress state and damage level [1]:

$$\frac{\delta D}{\delta N} = A \frac{\sigma^\alpha}{(1-D)^\beta}$$

where D is the local damage state at any point in the bar (ranging from 0 to 1), σ is the maximum stress at any point in the bar, N is the number of fatigue cycles, and A , α , and β are adjustable parameters. Many equations have been proposed to relate local damage state (D) to the bulk properties of a composite [1,3,4,5,6]. In this work, the modulus at each point in the bar (E) is given by:

$$E = E_0(1-D)$$

where E_0 is the initial modulus of the undamaged material. The linear beam equations are then solved at each point in the bar using standard finite element techniques. Bulk properties such as apparent beam stiffness are determined by integrating over the entire bar.

Figure 3 shows an example of the two dimensional distribution of damage at failure (D) predicted by this model for a typical three point bend fatigue simulation. Figure 4 shows the predicted change in apparent bending stiffness throughout the fatigue test for the same simulation. This type of model can be used to directly predict fatigue performance by inputting measured damage accumulation information obtained from our acoustic emission experiments. It also allows us to develop a fundamental understanding of how damage accumulates and propagates in composite materials.

SUMMARY

This paper briefly outlines some of the experimental and theoretical programs underway in our laboratories to understand fatigue performance and damage accumulation in glass reinforced thermoplastic and thermoset composites. Specifically, an experimental program in monitoring the spatial and time distribution of accumulated fatigue damage using acoustic emission techniques is discussed. Also, the development of a simple model which relates accumulated damage to changes in bulk properties such as apparent bending stiffness is outlined. The experimental and modeling results from these two programs will be discussed in more detail in the oral presentation.

Figure 3 Predicted damage accumulation at failure for a typical three point bend flexural fatigue simulation.

Figure 4 Predicted apparent bending stiffness versus fatigue cycles for a typical three point bend flexural fatigue simulation.

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